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Emergent and Generative Grounded Theory for Practice-Based Applied and Professional Research

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ABSTRACT

This academic paper presented the problem regarding the gap among theory, research, and practice, as there is an over-emphasis on the use of empirical data for theory verification only. This article responded to the following questions: What is grounded theory? What are the debates regarding the use of grounded theory? What are the different variants of grounded theory? Is grounded theory imperatively inductive, as a consequence of which it does not use a pre-conceived theory? This paper is an integrative literature review that explored the different arguments regarding the use of grounded theory in research.

Keywords: Grounded Theory, Qualitative Research, Research Methodology, Research Methods

Problem Statement

This paper highlights the problematic hegemonic practice of merely copying, pasting, and utilizing pre-existing theories to most positivistic research work with a view to match data with a given theory, thereby confirming or falsifying (Popper, 2002) the theory used. This paper fills the gap in research, theory, and practice by proposing the resort to the employment of grounded theory, which is a paradigm shift (Kuhn, 2012) in the conduct of research.

Filling the gap, especially in qualitative research, is moving away from the hypothetico-deductive research paradigm to inductive theory the use of the inductive grounded theory paradigm. See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Filling the Gap in Research, Practice, and Theory

Research Questions

This article answered these research queries:

- What is grounded theory in general?
- What are the debates regarding the use of grounded theory?
- What are the different variants of grounded theory?

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this paper was to explain the concept of grounded theory in general, to explain the split in the theory, and to show the assortments of grounded theories that have mushroomed henceforth.

Contributions of the Study

This paper rejects the argument according to which the dominant monolithic a priori or deductive approach is the only way by research could be conducted. Especially for scholar-practitioners, research must be used as a tool to improve social reality, not simply to prove that a theory is correct. Instead of blindly accepting and utilizing ready-made deductive theories only, especially for qualitative research, I propose the employment of the different iterations of the grounded theory in research, especially for scholar-practitioners. Rather than merely applying existing theories, scholar-practitioners have so much data to offer while conducting research, *au fur et à mesure*, for conceptualization and theorizing a posteriori from the ground up, not top down.

Coverage of the Study

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This section presents the scope, limitation, and delimitation of the study. The scope of this paper was grounded theory as such. It is limited to the exposition of the different variants of grounded theory. This paper does not discuss other types of inductive research. See Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Coverage of the Study

LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review provided an overview of the sources of data for data collection regarding grounded theory. Glaser and Strauss wrote the groundbreaking exposition on grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Strauss and Corbin further developed grounded theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

Charmaz, Babchuk, and other authors who have contributed to the development and popularization of the grounded theory (Babchuk, 2008; Charmaz, 2014). Today, the grounded theory joins the pantheon of qualitative research methodology, as they are grosso modo cast in stone in textbooks (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Wertz et al., 2011).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is neither a laundry list nor an annotated bibliography but a critical evaluation of seminal writings on grounded theory. This article is an integrative literature review, the purpose of which was to analyze, critique, and synthesize the key pieces of literature (Torraco, 2005, 2016) related to grounded theory. Aside from providing the key elements of the grounded theory that each set of authors discuss, this paper makes connections and spot the changing trends in the development of grounded theory.

This article discussed different sets of grounded theory, both the seminal work and the state-of-the-art work to provide a big picture of the grounded theory. The classical work provided insight into the reasons for which grounded theory was developed in the first place (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), while the revisions and cutting-edge publications provided new models of conducting grounded theory research, as well as lead to critical reflections for the development of new research agenda in further development of grounded theory (Torraco, 2005).

Based on the foregoing, this literature review performed three tasks: one, it reviewed the

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relationships among the related literature; two, it critiqued the different sets of literature, discussing the contributions as well as gaps in the literature; and, three, it synthesized the whole set of literature by providing not only a taxonomy but also a meta-theory of grounded theory. Thereafter, an integrated Figure that summed up the integrated literature review.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section responded to all the research questions related to grounded theory.

Findings

Grounded Theory in General. This first section in the Findings replied to the first research question: What is grounded theory in general? Glaser and Strauss were the pioneers of grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). They collaborated on a project at the University of California in San Francisco (UCSF) where they guided nursing students in studying patients who were dying in the hospital, for which they co-authored their pathbreaking book titled *Discovery of grounded theory* (1967).

In essence, Glaser and Strauss criticized the over-stress on the deductive research in which verification of theory was primary. They were dissatisfied with the lack of focus on the unearthing of concepts and theories which are grounded on the data of the research. Being involved in the profession that actually needs to be practical use and application of research for the amelioration of the conditions of dying patients, Thus, they counterpoised hypothetico-deductive theory with inductive grounded theory. See Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Rejection of Hypothetico-Deductive Theory and Promotion of Grounded Theory

They wrote:

Theory should “be useful in practical applications—prediction and explanations should be able to give the practitioner understanding and some control of situations” thought the “systematic discovery of theory from the data of social research” (Glaser & Strauss, 1967)

In their trailblazing work (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), the co-authors Glaser and Strauss rejected traditional positivist quantitative methodologies; instead, they utilized rigorous systematic procedures in order to discover theory from data, neither verifying pre-existing hypotheses nor confirming pre-determined theories (Babchuk, 2009a). Qualitative, inductive, and rigorous, as well as building on constant comparative method and simultaneous data collection analysis, grounded theory is both the results of the process of research is the research process itself (Babchuk, 2009a).

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Analytic induction and constant comparative method refer to the discovery of common features and regular trends in qualitative data with a view to provide explanation as well as to the sighting of other circumstances to examine the generality of the explanation (Kratwohl, 1997). As the research advances, fieldnotes are coded. New instances of a concept or dimension are sought until nothing new could be learned about it. Thenceforth, these emerging concepts are linked with other concepts with a view to develop an explanatory theory which is constantly compared with new data that continually emerge from the field work. Discrepancies lead to the revision of the theory in order to improve understanding of social reality (Kratwohl, 1993).

The epistemological roots of Glaser and Struss differed. Rigorous quantitative methods of Paul Lazarsfeld at Columbia University as well as the middle-range theories that Robert Merton championed have influenced Glaser. U.S. pragmatism and symbolic interactionism of the field research of the Chicago school have influenced Strauss (Babchuk, 2009b). Grounded theory started as a polemic against traditional positivism in sociology, which forced data into predetermined categories and theories thereby over-emphasizing the use and confirmation of theory (Merton, Reader, & Kendall, 1957). As a result, there is a lack of discovering actual data from which categories could emerge, which leads to the emergence of a new theory grounded on the data (Babchuk, 2009a).

Clearly, Glaser and Strauss have come up with the revolutionary new grounded theory as a result of their dissatisfaction with both the traditional mainstream hegemonic hypothetico-deductive research framework and the limitations of qualitative research. Henceforth, there is a rivalry between traditional positivistic quantitative research and qualitative grounded theory (Babchuk, 2009a).

Grounded Theory is Now Janus-Faced. From the emergence of a new grounded theory, the co-authors later split into two very divergent camps. The original house of emergent grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) is now divided into the Glaserian model on the one hand and the Straussian model on the other hand. For this reason, grounded theory henceforth is “not a unified framework” anymore (Denzin, 2007) See Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Glaser and Strauss Split Grounded Theory into Two

Glaser maintained the original classical model of emerging grounded theory. Strauss partnered with Corbin to develop the systematic or the forcing model of ground theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Glaser engages in theory generation, while Strauss subsequently participates in theory

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verification. On the one hand, Glaser depended heavily upon on eighteen theoretical coding families (Glaser, 2007, 2008; Glaser & Strauss, 2006, 2010). The eighteen coding families are the following: causes-consequences, concepts, consensus, culture, cutting point, degree, dimension, interaction, mainline, means-goal, model, process, reading, self-identity, theory, type, strategies, and unit (Glaser, 2007, 2008; Glaser & Strauss, 1967, 2006, 2010).

On the other hand, Strauss and Corbin count heavily upon an exceedingly structured coding architype of open, axial, and selective coding that forces data to complete conceptual description (Corbin & Strauss, 2015; Strauss & Corbin, 1998) which returns to the verification of theory, which Glaser and Strauss originally tried very hard to evade. Glaser criticized his former co-author Strauss, firstly, for using pre-conceived rules and procedures of positivistic pre-structured coding paradigms. Glaser criticized Strauss, secondly, for engaging in providing detailed descriptions only, not explanation. Clearly, there is now a rupture between Glaser who focuses on the role of grounded theory in explanation and Strauss who concentrates on the role of grounded theory in full conceptual description only.

Different Variants of Grounded Theory. This section responded to the third research question: What are the different variants of grounded theory?

From the original emergent grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), Glaser remained in the pioneering original tradition. Co-author Strauss diverged from the original understanding of grounded to form the pre-structured systematic grounded theory (Corbin & Strauss, 2015; Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Thereafter, there is a new divide. On the one hand, there is objectivist grounded theory. On the other hand, there is interpretivist grounded theory, the paradigm of which is that human understanding of reality is socially constructed. Thus, focus on interpretivist grounded theory is on phenomena, experiences, and relationships.

The new wave of grounded theory (Bryant & Charmaz, 2007, 2019) is opposed to the objectivist positivist and postpositivist paradigm, which was used in the original framework (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) as well in the splinter grounded theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Some of the anti-positivist paradigms that emerged, which resort to grounded theory, include interpretivism (Charmaz, 2014) and postmodernism (Clarke, 2005; Clarke, Friese, & Washburn, 2015, 2018; Clarke, Washburn, & Friese, 2022). Being anti-positivistic, grounded theory methodology rests on the principle according to which knowledge is not abstract, neutral, and objective. Rather, knowledge is constructed and the researchers co-construct knowledge (Charmaz, 2014). Thus, grounded theory is engaged in “an interpretive portrayal of the studied world, not an exact picture of it” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 10). Constructivist grounded theory methodology is not based upon a fixed set of sternly tracked rubrics, but upon a flexible set of principles and practices (Charmaz, 2006). Based on the preceding statements, there are four major variants of grounded theory today. See Figure 5 below:

Figure 5: Four Major Grounded Theory Methodology

Glaser criticized (Glaser, 2007) the constructivist grounded theory of Charmaz as engaged in mere capture of description. Accordingly, Glaser insisted that the grounded theory of Charmaz is not dissimilar with the comprehensive description of concepts of Strauss and Corbin. Postmodern grounded theory, on its part, does not seek to analyze social processes, but is engaged in situational analysis for the purpose of illuminating social situation (Clarke, 2005; Clarke et al., 2015, 2018, 2022).

Today, there are currently many variants of grounded theory. Glaser and Strauss spearheaded the following models of grounded theory: positivist, post-positivist, and objectivist. Charmaz and Clarke carved the path to the development of the constructivist, postmodern, and situational grounded theory. In addition, qualitative data analysis software, such as NVivo is used for the generation of computer-assisted grounded theory. See Figure 6 below:

Figure 6: Different Variants of Grounded Theory

Discussion

Grounded theory is useful for practitioners in the professional fields. All artistic and professional fields, including business, communication, community development, dance, education,

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 environmental human resource development, law, management, marketing, medicine, nursing, performance, and social work aim for improvements in their work, services, and benefits to their clientele or communities. Using a pre-existing hypothetico-deductive theory only serves to confirm or reject that given theory. Thus, such a priori logic is not of practical use for actually trying to improve social realities for the amelioration of human conditions. The output of such deductive research only serves the selected theory, but not practical in solving real-world problems.

Grounded theory as a methodology is based primarily on first gathering facts, after which a grounded theory is produced as an output. For this reason, grounded theory methodology is useful in identifying trends based on the data gathered first, from which scholar-practitioners and professionals produce an inductive grounded theory.

Note that grounded theory is useful for qualitative research. However, grounded theory is not only useful for qualitative enquiries. In fact, Glaser had written a book on how to conduct quantitative grounded theory (Glaser, 2008).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Is grounded theory a qualitative research design (Creswell & Poth, 2018), a research approach (Creswell & Poth, 2018), a methodology (Glaser, 1998), or a family of methods (Bryant & Charmaz, 2007)? The answer is all of the above, depending on the authors of grounded theory. This paper is condensed in the following Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Summary of the Paper

Conclusion

Grounded theory is most relevant for scholar-practitioners and professionals engaged in applied research in different fields. It gives the researchers the opportunity first to collect data, after which

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they are coded and lead to the development of a grounded theory, based on the actual data on the ground.

Recommendations

Practice-based researchers will benefit from using inductive grounded theory to produce new knowledge from the actual data they collect from their constituents. They include people who are in the business of improvement the conditions of individuals (such as nurses and medical doctors), communities (community developers and social workers), students and schools (faculty), organizations (human resource developers), or customers (business people, managers).

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